

CREEP DEFORMATION AND CREEP RUPTURE OF FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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A theoretical analysis is presented which enables the prediction of the creep and rupture characteristics of a fibre reinforced composite from a knowledge of the creep behaviour of its components. The analysis is employed to show how a fibre composite can be designed to resist creep deformation and rupture. Experimental results reported to date are interpreted on the basis of the theory. It is shown that the relationships used to fit the experimental data are not dependent on the actual mechanisms that operate and therefore do not hold in general.

A series of creep and rupture tests have been carried out on tungsten wire and copper as well as on composites of tungsten wire reinforced copper produced by liquid metal infiltration. The tests on the composites were conducted at various applied stresses with different volume fractions of reinforcement. An IBM 1130 computer was used to plot the creep curves and rupture times predicted by the theory. These are found to be in good agreement with the experimental observations.

NOMENCLATURE

σ	stress	
σ_r	rupture stress	
ϵ	strain	
E	modulus of elasticity	
t	time	
h_0	initial length of composite	
V	volume fraction	
suffix m, f or c	denotes matrix, fibre or composite	
suffix o	denotes value on immediate application of load	

1. INTRODUCTION

A large proportion of the effort on fibre reinforced composites is directed towards developing a material for use at elevated temperatures where creep is a most significant factor. The mechanisms that lead to creep in a fibre composite have been analysed by de Silva [1], and the present paper gives a theoretical analysis, together with relevant experiments, to predict the creep curve and rupture time of a fibre composite from a knowledge of the creep behaviour of its components.

The composite considered is one composed of strong, aligned, continuous fibres of high elastic modulus embedded in a softer, ductile matrix. The characteristics of creep and relaxation in metals are taken to be as stated earlier [1]. It is important to note that the components of the composite are taken to obey any general creep relation, and in particular, that the creep rates displayed by the components are taken to be history dependent. This is because the stress variations in the components during creep, the creep curve of the composite and its rupture time are very sensitive to the nature of these creep relations.

The experimental rupture test results obtained to date have been found to yield two varieties of relationships shown schematically in Fig. 1. The first, Fig. 1(a), is that a linear variation is obtained when the composite rupture stress σ_c' is plotted against the logarithm of the time to rupture $(t_r)_c$, [2] - [5]. This is the sort of relationship observed for single metals at a constant stress. During creep of a composite, however, the matrix relaxes its stress with a continuous pre-stress and the fibres creep under an increasing stress [1]. Therefore in general we would not expect a linear relation between σ_c' and $\log(t_r)_c$. Though this is so it will be shown that in many cases, within limits, the creep functions involved give a variation approximating to a linear one.

The second experimental observation, Fig. 1(b), made in early studies of the effect of volume fraction (see for example [6], [7]), is that σ_c' varies linearly with V_f for a fixed time to rupture. This is equivalent to the assumption that σ_c' is given by

$$\sigma_c' = \sigma_f' V_f + \sigma_m' V_m \quad (1)$$

which is the rule of mixtures using the rupture stresses of the components.

Fig. 1 Schematic representation of the composite rupture relations observed experimentally by previous workers.

Fig. 2 Virtual displacements in time δt of the components of a continuously reinforced composite during creep.

Though Eq. (1) fits the experimental results in the particular cases it has been applied, it is not dependent on the actual mechanisms that operate and would not hold in general. This is because the stresses in the components of a composite vary during creep and further, Eq. (1) implies that fracture occurs in both components simultaneously while this is not so. Composite failure depends on initiation in one component, and subsequent failure of the second component under an increased load. It will be shown that the actual relation between σ_c' and V_f is quite complex but in some cases the values of σ_c' obtained would be close to those given by Eq. (1).

2. STRESS VARIATIONS AND CREEP CURVE OF COMPOSITE

Consider a continuously reinforced fibre composite at an elevated temperature T subject to an external stress σ_c in the direction of the fibres. The approach used is to analyse the initial processes that occur in the composite and determine how they achieve a balance to give a steady rate of creep in the composite. Steady state creep continues until rupture of the composite intervenes.

During creep the condition of the components alters as given by de Silva [1]. Referring to Fig. 2, let λ_t be the extension of the composite at any instant t. In the next small interval of time δt the matrix creeps a distance $\delta \xi$ under the stress in it σ_m at that instant. Then

$$\delta \xi = h_o \frac{d\epsilon_m}{dt} \delta t \quad (2)$$

where $\frac{d\epsilon_m}{dt}$ is the creep rate of the matrix at (σ_m, T) with its appropriate creep history. Similarly the fibres creep a distance $\delta \eta$ given by a similar expression

$$\delta \eta = h_o \frac{d\epsilon_f}{dt} \delta t. \quad (3)$$

To maintain material compatibility the composite extends an intermediate amount $\delta \lambda_t$.

Therefore during the interval δt the matrix relaxes its stress by $(-\delta \sigma_m)$ given by

$$-\delta \sigma_m = E_m \left(\frac{\delta \xi - \delta \lambda_t}{h_o} \right) \quad (4)$$

During this period the fibres increase their stress and, since the external load remains constant, equating forces we have the condition

$$E_m \left(\frac{\delta \xi - \delta \lambda_t}{h_o} \right) V_m = E_f \left(\frac{\delta \lambda_t - \delta \eta}{h_o} \right) V_f. \quad (5)$$

Solving these equations we find that

$$-\delta \sigma_m = A \left(\frac{d\epsilon_m}{dt} - \frac{d\epsilon_f}{dt} \right) \delta t \quad (6)$$

where

$$A = \frac{E_m E_f V_f}{E_f V_f + E_m V_m}.$$

The increase in fibre stress $\delta \sigma_f'$ is obtained from

$$\delta \sigma_f' = - \frac{V_m}{V_f} \delta \sigma_m. \quad (7)$$

It is now necessary to determine expressions for the creep rates of the components. It has been found (see [6]) that the creep rate of a material depends on, besides σ and T, either the previous plastic strain (strain dependent) or on the time for which it has been held at temperature (time dependent). To continue with the argument we assume that the components are time dependent. The case when they are strain dependent is given in the Appendix.

Let constant stress creep tests (at a fixed temperature T) on the matrix yield the relation

$$\epsilon_m = \gamma_m(\sigma_m, t) \quad (8)$$

giving the creep stain at any time for a given stress. Due to the dependence on its previous history, in a variable stress case Eq. (8) would not fix ϵ_m uniquely for a given (σ_m, t) combination. However, Eq. (8) defines an (ϵ, σ, t) surface for the material and the creep rate corresponding to a chosen (σ_m, t) combination is fixed by the gradient at the corresponding point on the surface. The direction of the gradient is that of the (σ_m, t) path through the point concerned. Thus the creep rate of the matrix is given by

$$\frac{d\epsilon_m}{dt} = \frac{\partial \gamma_m}{\partial \sigma} \frac{d\sigma_m}{dt} + \frac{\partial \gamma_m}{\partial t} \quad (9)$$

Similarly for the fibres

$$\frac{d\epsilon_f}{dt} = \frac{\partial \gamma_f}{\partial \sigma} \frac{d\sigma_f}{dt} + \frac{\partial \gamma_f}{\partial t}$$

Differentiating Eq. (7) with respect to t and substituting,

$$\frac{d\epsilon_f}{dt} = -\frac{V_m}{V_f} \frac{\partial \gamma_f}{\partial \sigma} \frac{d\sigma_m}{dt} + \frac{\partial \gamma_f}{\partial t} \quad (10)$$

Substituting from Eq. (9) and Eq. (10) into Eq. (6) and simplifying we obtain,

$$-\frac{d\sigma_m}{dt} = \frac{\frac{\partial \gamma_m}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \gamma_f}{\partial t}}{\left[\frac{1}{A} + \frac{\partial \gamma_m}{\partial \sigma} + \frac{V_m}{V_f} \frac{\partial \gamma_f}{\partial \sigma} \right]} \quad (11)$$

This gives the variation of σ_m with time and substitution in Eq. (7) yields the variation of σ_f .

In addition, from Eq. (2) and Eq. (4) we have

$$-\frac{d\sigma_m}{dt} = E_m \left(\frac{d\epsilon_m}{dt} - \frac{1}{h_0} \frac{d\lambda_t}{dt} \right)$$

Substituting from Eq. (9) and simplifying

$$\frac{1}{h_0} \frac{d\lambda_t}{dt} = \left(\frac{1}{E_m} + \frac{\partial \gamma_m}{\partial \sigma} \right) \frac{d\sigma_m}{dt} + \frac{\partial \gamma_m}{\partial t} \quad (12)$$

$\frac{d\sigma_m}{dt}$ is known from Eq. (11) and thus Eq. (12) gives the creep rate of the composite $\frac{d\lambda_t}{dt}$ at any instant.

As creep proceeds the rate of relaxation of the matrix (and hence its creep rate) continuously decreases while the creep rate of the fibres increases. Normally the creep rate of the composite decreases, and all three creep rates approach one asymptotic value. This is shown schematically in Fig. 3. Steady state creep will be recorded when we are sufficiently close to the asymptotic value. It is interesting to note that it is possible for the creep functions to make $\frac{d^2\lambda_t}{dt^2} > 0$. In such cases the composite creep rate increase with time, again to a common asymptotic value.

3. RUPTURE OF THE COMPOSITE

We now proceed to determine the point at which the composite ruptures. The approach used is to calculate the accumulation of damage in each component due to it being subjected to stress and temperature. It is then possible to determine which component reaches its rupture condition first. If this is the matrix it normally corresponds to failure of the composite because the medium used to make the fibres efficiently load bearing is no longer available. In addition, in most practical cases the damaged condition of the

Fig. 3 Schematic representation of the variation of the creep rate of the components with time during creep of a continuously reinforced composite.

Fig. 4 The calculated variation of the stresses in the components and the accumulation of damage in them as creep proceeds in a selected composite (see Section 4).

matrix accelerates failure in the fibres and exposes them to environmental attack. In cases where the fibres are expected to continue carrying the (total) load alone for a reasonable period of time, the accumulation of damage in the fibres can continue to be calculated until they rupture.

Under certain conditions, normally at low volume fractions, the fibres become subject to very high stresses and could reach their rupture condition first. It is then necessary to continue calculating the accumulation of damage to the matrix with it now carrying the entire load. The composite fails in this case when the matrix reaches its rupture condition.

Now, suppose that constant stress rupture tests at a fixed temperature T on the components yield a relation between time to rupture t_r and the applied stress σ in the normal manner. t_r usually decreases exponentially with σ . In general let us assume that the relation for the matrix at a temperature T is $t_r = \beta_m(\sigma)$.

Since the stresses in the components of the composite vary with time we make use of the life fraction rule first introduced by Robinson [7] and substantiated experimentally on many occasions. The relative damage to the matrix if it is under a stress σ for a time δt is $(\delta t/t_r)$ where t_r is the time to rupture under a stress σ at that temperature. Therefore the matrix in the composite ruptures when

$$\int \frac{dt}{t_r} = 1$$

i.e.

$$\int \frac{dt}{\beta_m(\sigma_m)} = 1 \quad (13)$$

where $\sigma_m = f(t)$ is given by Eq. (11). A similar expression can be obtained for the fibres.

4. EVALUATION OF THE CREEP CURVE AND RUPTURE TIME OF A PRACTICAL FIBRE COMPOSITE

In a practical fibre composite the integration of the equations, especially Eq. (13), may be very complex. It is then necessary to solve them numerically by selecting appropriate time intervals, these being small at first and longer as the variations become smaller.

To illustrate the application of the theory and to examine certain important aspects let us now evaluate the rupture characteristics of a fibre composite containing continuous fibres of elastic modulus $20.69 \times 10^4 \text{ MN/m}^2$ in a matrix of modulus $6.90 \times 10^4 \text{ MN/m}^2$, at a temperature $T^\circ\text{C}$.

The outline of the procedure is as follows:

(i) From constant stress creep data on the components select the 'creep strain-time' and 'time to rupture-stress' relations at $T^\circ\text{C}$. To proceed with the example let these be

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_m &= (\epsilon_0)_m + 2.4 \times 10^{-8} \sigma^{2.5} t^{0.38} + 6 \times 10^{-8} e^{6.53 \times 10^{-2} \sigma} t \\ (t_r)_m &= 1.24 \times 10^3 e^{-6.53 \times 10^{-2} \sigma} \\ \epsilon_f &= (\epsilon_0)_f + 14.7 \times 10^{-9} \sigma^2 t^{0.17} + 1.2 \times 10^{-9} e^{2.9 \times 10^{-2} \sigma} t \\ (t_r)_f &= 31 \times 10^4 e^{-2.76 \times 10^{-2} \sigma} \end{aligned}$$

where σ is in MN/m^2 and t is in hours.

The values of the material constants selected are typical. In this case they approximate to those of steel wires in an aluminium alloy matrix.

Note that these relations are of a very general nature. The components, in addition, are taken to be time dependent in their creep behaviour.

- (ii) Select an applied stress σ_c and V_f . Obtain σ_m and σ'_f using

$$\sigma_c = \sigma'_f V_f + \sigma_m V_m.$$

(iii) In the first time interval, creep $\epsilon-t$ relations usually give an infinite creep rate at $t=0$, see Eq. (9) and Eq. (10). Therefore, remembering the components are at this point virgin material, use Eq. (6) in the form $-\delta\sigma_m = A(\delta\epsilon_m - \delta\epsilon_f)$ to obtain the fall in matrix tensile stress. With the mean value stress in the interval thus obtained, repeat the computation to obtain a more accurate value of $(-\delta\sigma_m)$. The rise in fibre stress is obtained from Eq. (7).

(iv) For the next time interval (t_2-t_1) , obtain $\frac{d\sigma_m}{dt}$ from Eq. (11) using the mean time in the interval and the stress at $t=t_1$. The fall in matrix stress during (t_2-t_1) is given by $-\frac{d\sigma_m}{dt}(t_2-t_1)$. Repeat the computation using the mean value of stress from t_1 to t_2 thus obtained.

(v) Plot σ_m and σ'_f against time as in Fig. 4.

(vi) Compute the damage in each interval $\left[\frac{\delta t}{\beta_m(\sigma_m)}\right]$ using the mean matrix stress in that interval. Sum the damage in each interval to the preceding total damage. Repeat for the fibres and plot as in Fig. 4.

(vii) Obtain the creep curve λ_t against t (Fig. 5) using Eq. (12).

(viii) Repeat (ii) to (vii) using different values of σ_c and volume fractions of reinforcement. Plot σ'_f against $\log(t_r)_c$ for the different values of V_f (Fig. 6).

5. CREEP AND RUPTURE OF TUNGSTEN

WIRE REINFORCED COPPER COMPOSITES

A series of creep and rupture tests were carried out at 300°C on tungsten wire and copper as well as on composites of tungsten wire reinforced copper produced by liquid metal infiltration [8]. The tests on the composites were conducted at various applied stresses with different volume fractions of reinforcement. For comparison, an IBM 1130 computer was used to plot the creep curves and rupture times predicted by the theory.

To make the composites, cleaned and degreased 0.2 mm diameter cold drawn tungsten wire from Mullard Ltd, U.K. was placed in crucibles machined from high purity graphite obtained from Morganite Refractories, U.K. The wires were then infiltrated by melting spectrographically pure 99.999% copper purchased from Johnson Mathey & Co. Ltd, U.K. Liquid infiltration was carried out by lowering the crucible at a controlled rate through a furnace under a vacuum better than 10^{-4} mm of mercury produced by an Edwards High Vacuum Pump together with a gettering device containing magnesium. All tests on the individual components were carried out after they had been subjected to the same thermal cycle in the composite manufacturing unit.

The composites produced were examined for proper fibre-matrix bonding and adequate fibre distribution by extensive microsectioning and by carrying out a series of tensile tests under argon at 300°C using a Hounsfield Tensometer. As found by other workers the tungsten wire showed a spread in strength values and elongation so that a large number of tests were carried out giving an average tensile strength of 1373.6 MN/m² and an average failure strain of 0.8% at 300°C, while the tensile strengths of the composites were reproducible and obeyed the rule of mixtures.

Fig. 5 The calculated creep curve of a selected composite (see Section 4).

Fig. 6 The variation of composite rupture stress with rupture time as calculated for different volume fractions of reinforcement for a selected composite system (see Section 4).

The creep tests were carried out at 300°C using a Samuel Denison T-45 creep testing machine modified to take small specimens and to accommodate an argon atmosphere.

The series of creep and rupture tests on pure copper and tungsten wire yielded the following relationships at 300°C;

$$\epsilon_m = (\epsilon_o)_m + 4162.9 \times 10^{-10} \sigma^{2.3} t^{0.3}$$

$$(t_r)_m = e^{0.77(15.5 - 0.145\sigma)}$$

$$\epsilon_f = (\epsilon_o)_f + 9.10 \times 10^{-10} \sigma^{2.11} t^{0.15} + 3.128 \times 10^{-7} \sigma^{0.76} t$$

where σ is in MN/m² and t is in minutes.

It was found that in the case of the tungsten wire the variation of rupture life with applied stress during the period of the creep tests was very small. Accordingly, it was taken that the wires failed at their ultimate tensile stress at 300°C.

An IBM 1130 computer was programmed to carry out the procedure given in Section 4 utilising the above data, together with $E_f(300^\circ\text{C}) = 34 \times 10^4 \text{ MN/m}^2$ and $E_m(300^\circ\text{C}) = 10.88 \times 10^4 \text{ MN/m}^2$. This meant that when a selected volume fraction and applied stress were fed to the computer, the computer plotter would draw the predicted creep curve of the composite and the computer read-out would give the predicted rupture time.

Next, creep and rupture tests were carried out at various applied stresses on composites containing 2%, 20% and 40% of tungsten wires in copper. The experimental results are shown in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8, together with the computer predicted curves for comparison. The discontinuity in some of the theoretical creep curves for composites having $V_f = 2\%$ corresponds to fibre failure, subsequent to which the matrix creeps under the total load.

6. DISCUSSION

During creep of the composite the matrix relaxes its stress with a continuous pre-stress. Fig. 4 shows that the relaxation is rapid at first but reduces considerably much later. Since damage in the matrix increases with σ_m and is highly stress sensitive, the relaxation away of the matrix stress onto the stronger fibres is an important means of increasing the creep resistance of the composite. This again must be done as early as possible and thus a matrix having a large primary creep extension is desirable. It is also worth noting that, for a fixed σ_{m0} and σ_{f0} , $\frac{d\sigma_m}{dt}$ given by Eq. (11) is strongly dependent on the stress sensitivities of creep of the components.

Having relaxed the matrix stress onto the fibres we must now ensure that the fibres are not overloaded. When the matrix stress relaxes, the fibre stress increases by $(\frac{1-V_f}{V_f})\delta\sigma_m$ and, for a given $\delta\sigma_m$, there can be very large increases in σ_f as V_f is made small. This could give rise to rapid damage of the fibres leading to failure. To avoid this the simplest procedure is to increase V_f sufficiently. However, in doing so we reduce σ_{m0} and σ_{f0} for a given σ_c and thus, depending on the stress sensitivities of functions ψ_m and ψ_f , we may increase or decrease the amount of matrix stress we relax, see Eq. (11).

Let us now examine some of the features that emerged from the numerical example done in Section 4. From Fig. 4 it is seen that the fibres have suffered very little damage by the time the matrix fails. This, and the fact that the fibres do not fail first with $V_f = 80\%$ and 35% (see Fig. 6) where high stresses are applied, can be misleading. At a volume fraction of 5% and at relatively low stresses failure is initiated by rupture of the fibres as shown by the dotted line in Fig. 6. At lower stresses (for $V_f = 5\%$) due to

(a) Volume fraction 40%

(b) Volume fraction 20%

(c) Volume fraction 2%

Fig. 7 Comparison of the theoretical and experimental creep curves obtained for continuously reinforced copper-tungsten composites

(a) Volume fraction 40%

(b) Volume fraction 20%

(c) Volume fraction 2%

Fig. 8 Comparison of the theoretical and experimental creep rupture plots obtained for continuously reinforced copper-tungsten composites

the effect of the stress sensitivity of creep the matrix again becomes the failure initiating component.

Fig. 6 also shows that the constant V_f composite rupture points lie on a straight line for the components chosen, though for very small rupture times (not shown) they were found to deviate from linearity. Since the creep relations chosen for the components were quite typical, such linear composite rupture relations will be found normally but not necessarily always. In addition it is seen from Fig. 6 that the σ_c' against V_f relation will depend on the fixed rupture time selected. This relation was found to be not too far removed from Eq. (1), especially in the lower V_f range and for larger fixed rupture times. It appears, therefore, that we may in cases obtain an experimental σ_c' versus V_f plot being fitted by Eq. (1).

In Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 the creep curves and creep rupture plots predicted by the theory for tungsten wire reinforced copper composites are compared with the experimentally observed curves and rupture times. It is seen that the agreement is good, and well within the safety factor margins normally used in structural design. The reason for this is the use in the theory of general creep expressions for the components, together with history dependence. The good correspondence between theory and experiment indicates that not only does the theory hold, but that the procedure outlined in Section 4 can be used to assess the creep and rupture behaviour of a continuously reinforced fibre composite system, without the need to manufacture and creep test a large number of composites. It also means that, given a set of matrices and a set of fibres, a reasonable assessment can be made theoretically of the creep and rupture behaviour of the different composite systems that can be formed between them. This is provided, of course, that the creep properties of the individual components are known, and that these properties are not significantly altered when the component is in the composite. This latter effect may arise when the inter-fibre spacing is very small (less than about 50 microns) so as to produce dispersion strengthening effects in the matrix, or when there is a considerable chemical reaction between fibres and matrix.

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APPENDIX

The case of strain-dependent components

In this case, due to the dependence on prior plastic strain, for the components it is only possible to obtain a differential relationship between the creep variables. That is, we can only obtain relationships of the form $\frac{d\epsilon_m}{dt} = \chi(\sigma_m, e_m)$ and $\frac{d\epsilon_f}{dt} = \rho(\sigma_f, e_f)$ for a constant temperature, where e is the plastic strain undergone.

The plastic strain undergone by the matrix in the composite at any instant is

$$e_m = (e_0)_m + \frac{\delta}{h_0} \quad (14)$$

Now using Eq. (2) and Eq. (3), Eq. (6) can be written in the differential form

$$-\delta\sigma_m = \frac{A}{h_0} (\delta\delta - \delta\eta) \quad (15)$$

i.e.
$$\frac{\delta}{h_0} = \frac{1}{A} (\sigma_{m_0} - \sigma_m) + \frac{\eta}{h_0} .$$

We also have

$$\frac{d\epsilon_f}{dt} = \rho(\sigma_f, e_f)$$

and using Eq. (3) this becomes

$$\frac{d\eta}{dt} - h_0 \rho(\sigma_f, \frac{\eta}{h_0}) = 0 \quad (16)$$

in which from Eq. (7)

$$\sigma_f = \sigma_{f_0} + (\sigma_{m_0} - \sigma_m) \frac{V_m}{V_f} . \quad (17)$$

In addition, from Eq. (6)

$$\frac{d\sigma_m}{dt} + A(\chi - \rho) = 0 \quad (18)$$

in which from Eq. (14), Eq. (15) and Eq. (17)

$$\chi = \chi \left[\sigma_m, \left\{ (e_0)_m + \frac{1}{A} (\sigma_{m_0} - \sigma_m) + \frac{\eta}{h_0} \right\} \right]$$

$$\rho = \rho \left[\left\{ \sigma_{f_0} + (\sigma_{m_0} - \sigma_m) \frac{V_m}{V_f} \right\}, \frac{\eta}{h_0} \right] .$$

The solution of the simultaneous differential equations (16) and (18) gives $\sigma_m = f(t)$, the fall in matrix stress with time. The increase in fibre stress is then given by Eq. (7).

To obtain the creep curve of the composite we use Eq. (4) in the form

$$-\frac{d\sigma_m}{dt} = E_m \left(\frac{d\epsilon_m}{dt} - \frac{d\epsilon_c}{dt} \right)$$

i.e.
$$\frac{d\epsilon_c}{dt} = \chi + \frac{1}{E_m} \frac{d\sigma_m}{dt} .$$

This gives the creep rate of the composite at any instant since $\frac{d\sigma_m}{dt}$ is known. The rest of the analysis is similar to the time-dependent case.

In cases where one component is strain-dependent and the other time-dependent, an argument similar to the above analyses can be used.